

COACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN SPECIAL EDUCATION AT UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *The author of the article elaborates on this topic from a theoretical perspective, providing their own experience in testing coaching technologies in the teaching process of special pedagogy and speech therapy for university students. The article justifies the application of modern technologies in teaching speech therapy students, which contributes to their professional and personal growth. Special attention is given to the creation of personalized learning, which helps identify and develop students' strengths, overcoming their difficulties through positive reinforcement and active involvement in the learning process. The use of coaching enhances students' self-confidence, improves their communication skills, and develops self-regulation skills, which in turn contributes to better academic performance and self-development.*

Keywords: *experience, testing, coaching, technologies, process, teaching, speech therapy, students, professional, personalized learning, communication skills, development, self-regulation.*

Relevance of the Topic

Today, we stand on the threshold of a new era in education, an era where traditional approaches are no longer fully capable of addressing the challenges of the time. We live in a world that has drastically changed with the advent of the digital age and the subsequent Fourth Industrial Revolution. These changes demand a rethinking of the role and methods of teaching the younger generation.

Modern education faces fundamentally new challenges: the world that we once knew as stable, predictable, and simple has been replaced by an unstable, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous one. The COVID-19 pandemic has only accelerated these processes, ushering us into the BANI era—fragility, anxiety, non-linearity, and incomprehensibility. Jamaica Kasio, a futurist who coined this acronym to describe the modern reality, notes that volatility has turned into fragility, uncertainty has become anxiety, complexity has turned into non-linearity, and ambiguity - into incomprehensibility.

Global changes in the world and society necessitate the reform of the content of education in terms of its integration, humanization, and alternativeness.

In university of special education, there is an increasingly evident need for new forms of development and training for future special educators, aligned with the demands of the time and its challenges. The development of cognitive technologies for the implementation of personalized education in educational and pedagogical work, as well as the system of preparing teachers for this new approach, is an extremely important task for us. The task of personalized learning is officially declared in the standards of the second generation of education. The concept of higher education closely aligns with the concept of personalized learning and organically integrates into the competency profile of the modern teacher.

Modern technologies and learning tools, thanks to their extensive application in all spheres of societal life, are an important component of the continuous education system. Educational

technologies, serving as sources and transmitters of content in interactive and integrative formats, function as a tool for organizing and coordinating the interaction of subjects in the educational process, facilitating the learning, upbringing, and development of students. In contemporary science, more than 250 technologies used in organizing and managing the educational process are described. The understanding of the term "technology" in the context of the learning process is connected with the category of "activity." Learning tools, other structural technological elements, and knowledge of the laws of their functioning in contextual unity contribute to the systematic organization of activities and are the essence and substantive aspect of technologies.

Among the key technologies that determine the development of modern society are biotechnology, nanotechnology, social, information, and cognitive technologies, which are generators of remarkable ideas and discoveries capable of radically changing our lives (V.V. Guzeev, L.L. Rybnova, and others). The authors' classification includes technologies such as problem-based, concentrated, modular, developmental, differentiated, active, game-based learning, and critical thinking.

Cognitive technologies emerged at the intersection of several disciplines, such as cognitive psychology, artificial intelligence, neurophysiology, knowledge engineering, psycholinguistics, and psychosemantics. As a result of the synergy of these fields, cognitive science emerged as an interdisciplinary direction. One of the most impressive achievements in this field is the result of work in neurophysiology. Using modern scientific methods such as magnetic resonance imaging and positron emission tomography, scientists have mapped the brain, identifying areas responsible for storing different types of information. The activation of a specific brain region allows researchers to understand what a person is thinking and transfer this information to executive devices to perform necessary actions.

The modern informational environment is characterized by a large number of information sources transmitting an excessive volume of information, with its rapid updating leading to cognitive overload in individuals and necessitating the continuous acquisition of new knowledge and competencies. These factors demand a rethinking of didactic approaches and the integration of cognitive technologies into the educational process. These technologies will ensure:

- the development of new ways of processing and understanding educational information by learners;

- the development of practical application skills for newly acquired knowledge in new situations and the creative development of knowledge;

- adequate assessment and self-assessment of competencies, individual goals, mental processes, and personality traits;

- the formation of a value-based attitude toward significant knowledge and competencies.

Researchers note that visualization plays a particularly important role in information transfer due to the vast potential of graphical images in the acquisition and comprehension of information. Cognitive visualization not only serves an informational but also a cognitive function. It aids in the perception and reflection of the subject of study, both in terms of its various aspects and as a whole. Cognitive visualization is the didactic foundation for developing mind maps, which are increasingly used in both general and special education and are integrated into corrective pedagogy.

One of the most effective and practiced innovative management mechanisms and approaches is coaching. There are several different definitions of coaching, each reflecting a

particular aspect. Coaching is a special form of consultation and individual support aimed at personal and professional growth. Coaching is a technology for unlocking a person's potential to maximize its effectiveness. Coaching is not just a technique used in specific circumstances; effective coaching is a management method, a way of interacting with people, and a way of thinking. Coaching doesn't teach; it helps people learn (Timothy Gallwey). Coaching is the art of helping to enhance the effectiveness, learning, and development of another person. It is based not on the coach's knowledge, experience, wisdom, or foresight, but on the person's ability to learn and act creatively (M. Downey). According to these definitions, coaching can be viewed both as a science and an art (in building trusting relationships), as a process, a technology, a method, and a new type of thinking. Coaching is a space free from advice, judgment, directives, or expert opinions. The coach, through effective open-ended questions, encourages the person to tap into their deep knowledge and internal resources, helping them find answers within themselves and thus activating the subject position. The methods and technologies of coaching allow for a clear understanding of the goal (formulated positively, within the control zone, ecologically sound, in SMART format) and the design of an individual path to achieve it, which inspires and unlocks the person's potential. Engaging with a person's values and creating a vision enables the achievement of the highest results, fostering personal growth, increased awareness, accountability for decisions, confidence, a new outlook on life, and much more. As specialists in education, we must recognize that our task today – is not only to transfer knowledge but also to teach students to think critically, be flexible and adaptive, and be capable of self-learning and self-development. Coaching technologies provide us with tools to achieve these goals.

In 2022, I completed a 72-hour online course for professional development on the topic "Coaching Technologies in Education: Experience of Finland."

Methods (Technologies). Throughout the 2023-2024 academic year, I, as a university teacher, tested my project "Application of Coaching Practices in Creating a Personalized Learning Environment as a Way to Improve the Quality of Education and the Effectiveness of Educational and Developmental Activities for Speech Therapy Students." Today, I would like to share some results of this project's implementation. The goal of the project was to develop and test a model of a personalized learning environment based on the application of coaching technologies. This model aims to form a value-oriented personal sphere, offering students a wide range of opportunities for personal and professional self-development within the educational process and providing technological and pedagogical conditions to improve the quality of education.

The main objective of the project was to create conditions for improving the personalities of all participants in the educational process during the course "Logopedia" for second-year students (28 full-time students and 220 part-time students).

The tasks I set for the project were:

to implement and use organizational and methodological technologies

to build an individual trajectory of professional development with the active use of coaching, cognitive, and ICT technologies in teaching this course to students.

The model for creating a personalized environment included four stages:

Stage 1 – Diagnostics:

I developed a questionnaire for speech therapy students to diagnose their motivations, such as why they chose this profession and where they learned about it.

Why did you choose the profession of a speech therapist? This question aimed to identify their motivations, interests, personal experiences, and commitment to the profession.

What attracted you to the profession of a speech therapist? This question aimed to uncover which aspects of the profession (helping people, working with children, scientific aspects, etc.) are most important to the student.

How did you learn about the profession of a speech therapist? This question helps understand how the student first encountered the profession: through family, school, acquaintances, media, the internet, etc.

Have there been any personal experiences or situations in your environment that influenced your choice? This helps uncover any personal connections or events that made the profession of a speech therapist appealing.

What qualities do you think are necessary for success in the profession of a speech therapist? The goal is to determine what characteristics students deem important for this profession.

These questions help understand the students' motivations, their approach to the profession, and the sources of information that influenced their choice.

Stages 2-3 – Building the System: The use of technologies for creating individual professional development trajectories for speech therapy students, with active application of coaching, cognitive, and ICT technologies during the teaching of the course in speech therapy, involves creating a comprehensive approach. This approach not only fosters academic learning but also supports the development of personal and professional qualities in students.

Here are some key stages and approaches for implementing such a system:

Coaching Approach: Coaching as a method which supports students in finding their own solutions, developing self-awareness, motivation, and the ability to self-learn. During the teaching of speech therapy students, the following coaching methods were used:

Personalized Conversations: Regular coaching sessions aimed at identifying the strengths and weaknesses related to mastering the subject matter of speech therapy and areas for improvement.

Goal Setting: Helping students formulate both short-term and long-term goals in their professional practice.

Reflection: Discussing successes and failures, developing self-regulation skills and critical thinking.

Building Individual Trajectories: Depending on the student's interests and abilities, the coach can offer various development paths (for example, an in-depth study of certain aspects of speech therapy). This approach creates a personalized and supportive learning environment that aligns with each student's individual professional goals and helps enhance their capabilities as future speech therapists.

Cognitive Technologies: The application of cognitive technologies helps speech therapy students develop analytical thinking, self-organization skills, improve information perception, and solve practical tasks. The following active learning methods were used:

Critical Thinking Stimulating Technologies: For example, brainstorming, teamwork, cubes, lotus, essays, inserts, clusters, discussions, case study analysis, and more. These methods encourage students to think critically and develop creative problem-solving skills.

Metacognition: Assisting students in developing awareness of their own thinking and learning processes, so they can approach problem-solving more effectively.

Use of Cognitive or Mind Maps: Students can use mind maps to structure information, organize knowledge in speech therapy, and plan their own developmental trajectory. The mind map method (developed by Tony Buzan, a British psychologist) is a technique for graphically representing perceived content, processing, and remembering various types of information. It involves using different charts, diagrams, images, symbols, color schemes, and notations to reflect new ideas, conclusions, and connections between them. According to Buzan's theory of **radiant thinking**, the perception and processing of visual information activates both hemispheres of the brain simultaneously. The right hemisphere processes the symbolic and image-based graphic information in its full diversity and complexity. As a result, images, representations, meanings, and interpretations of words and signs connect with each other through numerous associations, forming a complex network of relationships that resembles informational maps. This metaphorical representation of textual information fosters the formation of a cohesive understanding of the material, enhances imaginative thinking, and develops intuition and creativity. During the study of specialized disciplines, the following algorithm is suggested for constructing mind maps:

Step 1: Familiarize with the text, evaluate the scope of work, and create an outline containing the main key points of the topic, along with subtopics related to the core concepts that reveal its essence.

Step 2: Gather relevant information, such as selecting literature on the topic, categorizing it by sections, and identifying authors and their theoretical approaches to the issue.

Mind maps can also serve as a tool for systematizing and storing information. They foster associative thinking, helping students identify various elements of ideas and discover new, unconventional connections. This approach not only aids in the organization of knowledge but also encourages creative and innovative thinking, which is essential for developing professional skills in speech therapy. Thus, mental maps, as an element of cognitive technologies in the educational process, help analyze and memorize information by activating both hemispheres of the brain. Mind maps ensure conscious and strong assimilation of the content of education and the improvement of cognitive, informational, communicative, and professional competence of speech therapy students. ICT technologies (Information and Communication Technologies). Modern ICT can significantly improve the quality of education, making it more personalized and accessible. The integration of ICT into the speech therapy course contributes to better interaction between students and the material, and allows for the introduction of innovative approaches; multimedia resources: videos, audios, and animations for visualizing speech therapy techniques, which help students improve their perception and retention of the material; gamification: introducing game elements into the learning process to increase student motivation. For example, the use of speech therapy games, speech task simulators, or virtual assistants for articulatory training, pronunciation exercises, and more; speech correction programs: software and resources for analyzing speech errors, modeling speech therapy sessions, allowing students to practice and improve their skills outside of classroom activities; electronic portfolios: students maintained portfolios in which they recorded achievements, self-analysis, individual development plans, results of practical sessions, technologies used, and necessary materials, allowing them to track their progress and adjust their learning trajectory.

Fig. 1. Mind maps for the discipline "Verbal and Non-verbal Communication" on the topic "Dactyl Speech."

4th stage – Analysis or Evaluation and Monitoring of Learning: Monitoring of speech therapy students was conducted during the periods of intermediate, final, and summative assessments. Evaluation using ICT: Software tools for testing, diagnostics, and monitoring results allowed me to promptly receive data on student achievements. I also continuously conducted formative and summative assessments: ongoing feedback through coaching sessions, online tests, assignments, discussions, and reflection allowed tracking students' knowledge, skills, and competencies (KSC) at all stages of their professional development. At each stage, various activities were carried out: surveys, team formation, distribution of responsibilities, and setting goals and tasks for each team member. During the implementation stage, students learned to work with new information and educational resources: lecture texts on speech therapy, textbooks, speech therapy albums, ICT (with slides), building a system for tracking results and outcomes of new quality—coaching the educational environment, and the portfolio was updated. During each module of the program, students independently created projects for open lessons using team-based methods and conducted them. Upon completing practical sessions, they wrote essays as a conclusion.

Conclusion

The main goal of Uzbekistan's education system, as defined in the national educational standard, is to foster the upbringing, social and pedagogical support for the development of a highly moral, responsible, creative, initiative-driven, competent specialist, and citizen of Uzbekistan.

The teaching system at universities, which incorporates coaching, cognitive, and ICT technologies, allows for the construction of individual professional development trajectories for speech therapy students. This comprehensive approach not only facilitates the acquisition of theoretical knowledge but also the development of key practical skills essential for successful professional activity in special and inclusive education.

We need to analyze the outcomes in more detail, work on the trial implementation, and describe the results. However, it is already clear that many of the coaching approaches and technologies are applicable in universities, helping students understand the purpose of learning, fostering engagement, enhancing motivation for self-development, and increasing responsibility for results.

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